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List of Acronyms

ADC	Analog Digital Conversion
D	Deliverable
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron experiment
FD	Forbush Decrease
FM	Failure Mode
G4VM	Geant4 Virtual Machine
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
HET	High Energy Telescope
ICME	Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection
NM	Neutron Monitor
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SSD	Solid State Detector
TO	Technical Objective
WP	Work Package
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
COSPIN	COsmic ray and Solar Particle INstrumentation
PM	Photomultiplier
SFS	Selected Flight Spare
SFM	Selected Flight Model
PMT	Photomultiplier
PHA	Pulse Height Analysis

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Executive Summary

This work presents the validation and application of a [GEANT4](#)-based simulation model for the [KET](#) instrument onboard the Ulysses spacecraft. Extensive ground-based calibration measurements were used to benchmark the simulated detector response for electrons and protons over a broad energy range. The comparison demonstrates that the simulation reliably reproduces the measured pulse-height distributions, angular acceptance, and coincidence behavior of the instrument.

The validated model enables the computation of omnidirectional particle response functions under the assumption of isotropic particle distributions. These response functions provide the basis for converting measured count rates into physical particle fluxes. The analysis shows that contamination effects are generally small and well understood, with proton contamination in electron channels becoming relevant only at the highest energies. Overall, the derived response functions constitute a robust foundation for the quantitative interpretation of [KET](#) measurements of Solar Energetic Particles ([SEPs](#)) and Galactic Cosmic Rays ([GCRs](#)).

1 Introduction

The SPECification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (**SPEARHEAD**) project aims to address key challenges in understanding the origin, acceleration, and transport of high-energy particles in the heliosphere. Central scientific questions include: (1) how protons are accelerated beyond 100 MeV and electrons beyond 1 MeV in solar eruptions, (2) how release times and energy spectra of near-relativistic particles are determined, and (3) how coronal and interplanetary structures modulate the transport of highly energetic particles. To support these goals, **SPEARHEAD** defines Technical Objective (**TO**) that focus on the derivation of accurate particle fluxes, the cross-calibration of different spacecraft instruments, and the integration of high-energy particle measurements with plasma modeling and context data.

Within this framework, Work Package (**WP**) 2 is dedicated to the computation of instrument response functions, which form the basis for accurate particle intensity measurements. Many high-energy detectors aboard heliophysics missions — including Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (**SOHO**)/Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (**EPHIN**), **SOHO**/Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron experiment (**ERNE**), Solar Orbiter/High Energy Telescope (**HET**), BepiColombo/Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer (**SIXS**), and Ulysses/**KET** — require detailed modelling of their detection efficiencies. These efficiencies link the measured count rates to the underlying physical particle intensities. In general, particle measurements consist of a set of observables (such as energy losses or detected photon counts), typically expressed as count rates C . At a given time t , the instrument is embedded in a radiation environment composed of multiple species of ions, electrons, and photons. The unknown particle intensities $J_\alpha(E, \omega, x, t)$ depend on kinetic energy E , direction of arrival ω , spatial position x , particle species α , and time t . The relationship between the measured count rates and the ambient particle intensities is given by the Sullivan equation (**Sullivan 1971**),

$$C(x, t_0) = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T} dt \int_S \hat{r} \cdot d\sigma \int_\Omega d\omega \int_0^\infty dE \sum_\alpha \varepsilon_\alpha(E, \sigma, \omega, t) J_\alpha(E, \omega, x, t), \quad (1)$$

which incorporates the detection efficiency ε_α , instrument geometry, and allowed directional acceptance. As efficiency depends on the detector design, materials, energy thresholds, and electronics, Monte Carlo simulations using the **GEANT4** toolkit are required to model particle interactions and compute the effective response. These simulations must then be validated through comparison with laboratory calibrations or cross-instrument studies.

Köberle et al. (2025a) provides the foundation for this document, which aims to deliver the validated response functions for the **KET** onboard the Ulysses spacecraft. **KET** is part of the Ulysses COsmic ray and Solar Particle INstrumentation (**COSPIN**) suite and is designed to measure energetic charged particles in interplanetary space, specifically electrons, protons, and helium nuclei across a wide energy range. Its primary scientific objective is to measure relativistic and near-relativistic electrons from a few MeV up to several GeV, enabling studies of **SEP** events and **GCRs**. Additionally, **KET** provides proton and helium measurements in several energy windows extending to rigidities above 2 GV, making it an indispensable instrument for studies of solar modulation and Forbush Decreases (**FDs**).

The **KET** detector system consists, as detailed below, of two major components: (1) an entrance telescope comprising two Solid State Detectors (**SSDs**) (**D1**, **D2**) and an aerogel Cerenkov detector (**C1**), which together define the geometrical acceptance and select particles with velocities exceeding $\beta > 0.938$, and (2) a calorimeter (**C2**) made of lead-fluoride, surrounded by anticoincidence detectors for background suppression. A scintillator (**S2**) located behind the calorimeter identifies electrons that are not fully absorbed. This combination of the telescope and calorimeter allows for species separation and energy estimation across a broad energy range (**Simpson et al. 1992**).

2 The Kiel Electron Telescope

The **KET** onboard the Ulysses spacecraft is part of the Ulysses **COSPIN** and was designed to study energetic charged particles in interplanetary space. Its primary objectives include measuring the energy spectra of electrons, protons, and helium across a wide energy range. The main focus was to measure the electron fluxes between a few MeV and below several GeV (for details see [Simpson et al. 1992](#)). To allow charge-sign-dependent studies on the solar modulation of **GCR**, it also provided measurements of proton and helium fluxes in several energy windows between a few MeV and above 2 GeV/amu (see studies of electrons and protons at a rigidity of about 2.5 GV by [Rastoin et al. 1996](#); [Ferrando et al. 1996](#); [Heber et al. 2002, 2003, 2009](#)) and comparison with ground based detectors as Neutron Monitors (**NMs**) ([Belov et al. 2001](#)). Within **SPEARHEAD**, the main focus of **WP2** is to generate Ulysses/**KET** products, including the determination of (ultra-)relativistic electron events and the flux of protons, with the latter being used to investigate Forbush Decreases (**FDs**) in **WP7**. In this deliverable, we therefore focus on stopping electrons with energies of up to 100 MeV (E12 in Tab. 1) and protons in the energy range from about 250 MeV to 2000 MeV (P190 in Tab. 1).

Figure 1: Left: Sketch of the **KET** (from [Dunzlaff \(2012\)](#)) Right: **GEANT4** model of the **KET** developed in [D2.4](#)

The detector system, illustrated in the left panel of Fig. 1, consists of two main components:

The entrance telescope which combines a Cerenkov detector, made of silica-aerogel (**C1** in Fig. 1) positioned between two semiconductor detectors (**D1** and **D2**). Together with the anti-coincidence, this configuration defines the geometry of the system and selects particles with velocities exceeding $\beta > 0.938$.

The calorimeter (C2) which is a lead-fluoride (**PbF2**) crystal with a thickness of 2.5 radiation lengths, and functions as a Cerenkov detector where electron showers develop. **C2** is surrounded by an anti-coincidence to reject particles that penetrate **C2** not within the opening angle defined by the entrance telescope. Lastly, a scintillator (**S2**) detects particles, i.e. electrons that are not absorbed by **C2**.

Channel	Type	MeV/nuc	Coincidence condition	Priority
P1	Proton	2.7 - 5.4	D11 D12 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	
	Proton	23.1 - 34.1		
	Alpha	2.3 - 2.7		
P4	Proton	5.4 - 23.1	D12 D13 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	
	Alpha	2.7 - 6.0		
	Alpha	20.4 - 34.2		
P32	Proton	34.1 - 116	D11 D12 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	1
P116	Proton	116 - 190	D10 D12 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	1
	Alpha	126 - 190		
P190	Proton	190 - 1880	D10 D11 C10 D20 D21 C20 C21 S20 A0	0
P4000	Proton	> 1880	D10 D11 C10 C11 D20 D21 C20 C21 S20 A0	0
A4	Alpha	6.0 - 20.4	D13 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	
A32	Alpha	34.2 - 116	D12 D13 C10 D21 C20 S20 A0	1
A116	Alpha	116 - 126	D12 D13 C10 D21 C20 S20 A0	1
A190	Alpha	190-1880	D11 D12 C10 D21 C20 S20 A0	0
A4000	Alpha	> 1880	D11 D12 C10 C11 D21 C20 S20 A0	1
E4	Electron	4 - 9	D10 D11 C10 C11 D20 D21 C20 S20 A0	1
E12	Electron	9 - 170	D10 D11 C10 C11 D20 D21 C20 S20 A0	3
E300	Electron	> 170	D10 D11 C10 C11 D20 D21 C21 S20 A0	2

Table 1: Acronyms, particle type, energy ranges of the KET with the corresponding coincidence conditions and the priority level. Discriminator thresholds for each detector shown in Fig. 1 are given in Tab. 2. XXX indicates that the signal needs to be smaller than XXX, with the first two letters indicating the detector, e.g. D1, and the third the threshold level.

Discriminator	Voltage / mV	PHA	ΔE / MeV	N_{ph}
D10	3.13	31	0.181	-
D11	18.54	85	1.075	-
D12	82.80	133	4.801	-
D13	373.60	183	21.660	-
D20	2.97	29	0.176	-
D21	18.28	84	1.085	-
C10	20.02	61	-	1.5
C11	603.23	212	-	45.9
C20	25.23	24	-	1.2
C21	687.77	168	-	33.1
S20	61.66	25	-	44.7
A0	60.94	-	-	21.8
A1	1263.44	-	-	450.2

Table 2: Discriminator thresholds as function of the detector (see Fig. 1) given in mV and as PHA number. For the two SSDs and the scintillation detectors S2 and A the values are given in MeV and for the Cerenkov detectors as numbers of photons N_{phot} . The relation between the latter and the PHA number is given in eq. 2.

Solid State Detector	a / keV	b	c	f	Δ / keV
D1	0.01223	0.39623	0.03055	1	25
D2	0.01705	-0.2792	0.03455	1	35
Cherenkov Detector	a / N_{phot}	b	c	f	Δ / N_{phot}
C1	2.5237	0.1416	0.02242	0.011	0.7
C2	1.4529	1.4225	0.02283	0.0103	0.5
Scintillation Detector ¹	a / N_{phot}	b	c	f	Δ / N_{phot}
S2	/	/	/	/	/
A	/	/	/	/	/

Table 3: Analog Digital Conversion (ADC) constants utilized in eq. 2. ¹ A detailed analysis of the Scintillation detector **S2/A** signal is not given in this study.

Based on the different responses of the individual detectors to various particle species and energies, six proton, five Helium, and three electron channels are defined and summarized in Tab. 1. The table provides the corresponding coincidence conditions utilizing the discriminator thresholds given in Table 2.

The physical signal energy loss or number of photons is digitized with the functions given in eq. 2. Here a , b and c are detector specific constants, as summarized in Tab. 3. These constants were determined either from calibration measurements with radioactive sources or from results derived from calibration at different accelerator facilities. As discussed below, we do not simulate the transport of photons in the light box or through the scintillator S1, nor do we take electronic noise into account. Therefore, a Gaussian or Poisson noise component was added to the simulation results, representing the quantity x in eq. 2 as detailed in the individual detector description.

$$PHA(x) = \frac{\ln(a \cdot x + b)}{c} \quad (2)$$

Semiconductors (D1, D2): $x = dE + \mathcal{N}(0, \Delta)$

Scintillators (A, S2): $x = N_{ph} \propto dE$

Cerenkov detectors (C1, C2): $x = Pois(f \cdot N_{ph}) \pm \Delta \cdot \sqrt{Pois(f \cdot N_{ph})}$

2.1 Simulation Setup

Köberle et al. (2025a) presents the development of a **GEANT4** simulation model specifically for the Ulysses/Kiel Electron Telescope (**KET**) instrument. It describes how the instrument's geometry and material composition were implemented using the Geometry Description Markup Language (**GDML**) schema within the **GEANT4** framework. The use of **GDML** ensures an accurate and structured representation of the physical setup for simulation purposes.

A special feature of the Ulysses/**KET** instrument is the usage of two Cherenkov detectors **C1** and **C2** that allow to discriminate electrons from ions over a wide energy range and deduce the energy of incoming particles based on the amount of Cherenkov photons created within the respective detector (Simpson et al. 1992).

To facilitate the computation of the response functions, the Geant4 Virtual Machine (**G4VM**) (<https://github.com/spearhead-he/G4VM>) was extended by including the direct computation of photons generated in the two Cherenkov detectors **C1** and **C2** by integrating Frank-Tamm Eq. 3. The corresponding runtime macro is summarized as follows and contains the new components:

/sd/optics/disp This command specifies the usage of a dispersive medium and requires three variables:

<ID> Detector ID of the Volume (25 for **C2**)

<path/to/refractive_index.txt> : the path and the name of a file that gives the refractive index $n(\lambda)$ as a function of the wavelength λ as used in the Frank-Tamm equation in eq. 3. The refractive index of PbF_2 is shown in the left panel of Fig. 2.

<path/to/QE.txt> the path and file name of a file that contains the quantum efficiency of the Photomultiplier (**PM**) as displayed in the right panel of 2.

/sd/optics/const A constant refractive index was used for **C1**, the quartz window of the **PM** and the glass surrounding the quartz window, within a lower and upper wavelength λ .

Below is an example of an adapted macro header (see Köberle et al. 2025b, for comparison):

```
/gdml/file gdml/KET/ket.gdml
...
/run/initialize

/sd/optics/disp 25 <path/to/refractive_index.txt> <path/to/QE.txt>

/sd/optics/const 26 1.55 300 700
/sd/optics/const 27 1.55 300 700
/sd/optics/const 1 1.066 300 700

# (optional) fold the same QE also for const-n:
# /sd/optics/const 26 1.55 300 600 <path/to/QE.txt>
# /sd/optics/const 27 1.55 300 600 <path/to/QE.txt>

/run/verbose 0
...
```

$$\frac{d^2N}{dx d\lambda} = \frac{2\pi\alpha z^2}{\lambda^2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta^2 n(\lambda)^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

N = Number of photons emitted	$\beta = v/c$
z = Charge	λ = Wavelength
α = Fine structure constant	x = Path length through medium

Figure 2: Left: refractive index of PbF₂. Inlet shows the relevant wavelength range to the sensitivity of the PMT. **Right:** Quantum efficiency of the Hamamatsu R1924 PMT. Refractive index data taken from <https://refractiveindex.info/?shelf=main&book=PbF2&page=Malitson>, Quantum efficiency data digitized from Hamamatsu (1992)

3 Ground based and inflight calibration

3.1 Accelerators

To calibrate **KET** and thus precisely investigate the individual detectors and their interactions, more than 600 measurements were carried out at various accelerators (see [Sierks 1988](#)). The focus was set on electron measurements, which is why three accelerators at ORME des Merisiers and Bonn were used, while for protons, only one accelerator was utilized at CERN. Unfortunately, not all measurement data are available and/or can be clearly assigned to the documented measurement runs. To calibrate the simulation results, the graphs of the calibration measurements presented in [Sierks \(1988\)](#) were digitized and compared. This was made more difficult by the fact that at the time of this work, the Selected Flight Model (**SFM**) was still planned for flight, and therefore fewer measurements were presented for the **SFS** that is onboard the spacecraft (for details see [Simpson et al. 1992](#), and references therein).

In order to compare and validate the simulation with the calibration measurements, the simulated beams must be adapted as closely as possible to the properties of the beams at the accelerator site. This task is particularly challenging since at the accelerator site typically the conditions are not optimal, due to parasitic particles, dispersion, or changes in beam intensity and beam axis with energy and the presence of other users. To emulate the conditions present at the accelerator site during the test campaigns, we follow the documentation provided by [Sierks \(1988\)](#) and [Iwers \(2000\)](#). The proton beam at CERN had an elliptical extension of approximately 150 mm horizontally and 100 mm vertically until the intensity dropped to $1/e$. Given the **KET** aperture radius of 17 mm, the beam can thus be directed at the full **KET** aperture with constant intensity to a good approximation. The Bonn accelerator was used for electron measurements in the range 30–1200 MeV. A small square collimator of 10 × 10 mm was placed 80 cm in front of the instrument aperture, which is why a constant intensity was projected from this area. A fanning out of the beam is expected due to the collimator which was considered by introducing a gaussian dispersion of 0.5° .

The beam characteristics for the accelerator site at ORME des Merisiers for electron measurements between 7.5 and 140 MeV are not given. To find proxy beam characteristics, the analysis of the count ratio measured in **D1** to those measured in **D2** presented in [Sierks \(1988\)](#) was analyzed. Figure 3 shows the count ratio over energy for the final results of the simulated beam shown as blue curve and for the measurements shown as black crosses. At low energies, scattering in **D1** and **C1** causes an increase of the **D1/D2** ratio, which becomes negligible at energies $\gtrsim 20$ MeV as indicated by the steady plateau of the count ratio C_r of ≈ 1.35 .

Figure 3: Count ratio of **D1** and **D2** for electrons measured at ORME as a function of energy. Black crosses mark measurements of the **SFS** model digitized from [Sierks \(1988\)](#), blue line represents simulation results.

Given a ratio of sensitive area between **D1** and **D2** of ≈ 1.5 [Sierks \(1988\)](#) concluded that the beam profile does not completely fill the area of **D1**. A constant intensity beam of the corresponding radius

however did not result in a good agreement of the simulated and measured C_r . A satisfactory proxy was manually found to be a source located 80cm in front of the aperture with gaussian intensity profile of width $\sigma_r = 0.86\text{cm}$.

The variation of the beam profiles of the different accelerators is visualized in Fig. 4 as 2D-histograms of incident particles in the x-y plane located at **D1**.

Figure 4: Illustration of the beam profiles used for the accelerators on ORME (left column), Bonn (central column) and at CERN (right column). Shown as 2D-histograms are incident particles in the x-y plane located at **D1**. 1D projections on the x-axis are shown on top.

3.2 Individual detector responses

3.2.1 Semiconductors D1/D2

For the Solid State Detector (SSD)s **D1** and **D2** no ground based calibration measurements of the SFS are documented. However, Tab. 2 gives the energy loss ΔE and the corresponding PHA number for the four and two threshold values in SSD **D1** and **D2**, respectively. These values have been copied into Tab. 4. In addition to these values, we validated the constants in eq. 2 by identifying two and four additional characteristic values for SSD **D1** and **D2**, respectively.

The first channels analyzed are called P32 and A32 (see Tab. 1) for stopping protons and helium, respectively. Characteristic energy loss distributions in SSD **D1** vs. SSD **D2** are shown in the upper and lower panels of Fig. 5 for protons (left) and helium (right) for in flight measurements and simulations, respectively. The first characteristic energy loss is given by the **D1** values when protons or helium penetrate SSD **D1** and generate a signal in SSD **D2**, but still stop in **D2**. The corresponding values are indicated by SP32 and SA32 as red horizontal lines and summarized in Tab. 4. The second characteristic energy loss is given by particles that have just enough energy to penetrate **D2**. This energy loss marks a sharp edge of the energy loss **D2** as indicated by the red vertical lines labeled PP32 and PA32.

The first channels that count penetrating protons and helium are the P116 and A116. The PHA distributions in SSD **D1** vs **D2** are shown in Fig. 6 for the measurements and simulations in the upper and lower panels. The expected distributions are a continuation of the distributions shown in Fig. 5 to lower energy losses and PHAs, respectively. Both distributions clearly show these extensions. The proton track extends even to lower values. This is most likely caused by the inefficiency of the Cherenkov detector **C2** for particles penetrating the instrument from the back. Note that the signatures of backward penetrating particles are evident because the energy losses in SSD **D1** vary from very low values to the highest ones for stopping particles, while the energy loss in SSD **D2** is nearly constant. This behavior is expected from

Source	PHA	ΔE / MeV
D10	31	0.181
D11	85	1.075
D12	133	4.801
D13	183	21.660
SA32	123	3.47
SP116	166	13.1
D20	29	0.176
D21	84	1.085
PP32	118	3.45
PA32	165	17.5
BPP116	163	16.4
BPA116	210	83.0

Table 4: Characteristic values that are needed to determine the calibration curve of the ADC chain for SSD D1 and D2.

Figure 5: Comparison of 2D-Histograms between In-Flight data from 1997 (upper row) and simulation results (bottom row) of energy deposition in **D1, D2 PHA** distributions for Channels P32 (left column) and A32 (right column). Particle populations labeled A and B in the left column mark backwards penetrating protons and helium contamination respectively. Simulation results of Population B particles are color coded in red. Red vertical lines in the P32 column mark the penetration point of protons in **D2**. Similarly, red vertical lines in the A32 column mark the penetration point of alpha particles in **D2**. Red horizontal lines in A32 mark stopping particles in **D2**.

Figure 6: Comparison between In-Flight data from 1997 (upper row) and simulation results (bottom row) of the energy deposition in **D1**, **D2** for channels P116 (left column) and A116 (right column). Particle populations labeled **A** color-coded in red in the left column marks helium particles not surpassing the D12 discriminator threshold. Population **B** and **C** labeled particles in the A116 column depict backwards penetrating protons and deuterons respectively, surpassing the D12 discriminator threshold. Red vertical lines shown in P116 and A116 mark backwards penetrating particles stopping in **D2** for protons and alpha particles respectively.

protons and helium that penetrate the instrument from the back. Thus, the corresponding two values in **SSD D2** can be utilized to characterize the **ADC** behavior. The values determined are indicated by **BPP116** and **BPA116** in Tab. 4, respectively. Note that the distributions in the two channels additionally show the track of helium in the proton channel and vice versa labeled **A** and **B** as well as deuterons in the A116 labeled **C**. This needs to be accounted for when analyzing the corresponding measurements.

KET provides a proton channel for energies above 2 GeV/nuc. This channel is a good proxy for the modulation of **GCRs** over the solar cycle. The corresponding distributions contain only relativistic particles. The simulated and measured distributions are shown in the left and right panels of Fig. 7, respectively, and can be used to monitor the stability of **SSDs D1** and **D2**. It provides distributions that allow us to determine the impact of additional electronic noise due to the distribution broadening caused by the electronics. Our analysis, based on such a comparison, leads to an electronic noise equivalent to 25 and 35 keV in **SSD D1** and **D2**, as summarized in Tab. 4. Note that, due to the onboard data processing, a few entries exist that give values slightly below and above the nominal threshold (for details see for example [Sierks 1988](#); [Heber 1997](#), and references therein).

Figure 7: Comparison of **D1,D2** 2D-Histograms between simulation (left) and In-Flight data from 1997 (right) in Channel P4000. 1D histograms for the individual detectors are given at each respective axis. Mean, median and standard deviation are summarized in the upper right corner of each subplot.

The mathematical description of the two SSDs in the G4VM virtual machine (Köberle et al. 2025a) are successfully validated against in flight measurements and can thus be used for the computation of the response functions.

3.2.2 Calibration and Analysis of the C2 Cherenkov Detector

Based on the wavelength-dependent refractive index data of PbF_2 (see left panel of Fig. 2), the spectrum of the emitted Cherenkov light is computed using Eq. 3 within the simulation. In order to account for the photon detection efficiency, the quantum efficiency of the Photomultiplier (PMT) is further included in the analysis. Since no datasheet could be found for the PMT type EMI D 507 used in the experiment, the quantum efficiency of a PMT with similar characteristics, the Hamamatsu R1924, was adopted. The corresponding quantum-efficiency curve is shown on the right side of Fig. 2. For each primary and secondary particle in the simulation, the calculated Cherenkov spectra are weighted with this function prior to integration and subsequent calculation of the corresponding PHA values.

Figure 8: PHA distribution in C2 of 50, 300 and 1000 MeV electrons and 4.15 GeV protons from the calibration (black curves) at Orme, Bonn and CERN, respectively. Shown as shaded distribution are the results of the simulation. The upper panels show the residual between the measurements and simulations, indicating a good agreement between calibration and simulation.

Fig. 8 shows the comparison of the resulting C2 Cherenkov PHA distribution for 50, 300, and 1000 MeV electrons and 4.15 GeV for protons as a blue shaded area, in comparison with calibration measurements digitized from Sierks (1988) (black lines) in the corresponding coincidence channels. The respective residuals of the normed distributions are shown above. It can be seen that the electron simulations are in excellent agreement with the calibration measurements. We performed such an analysis for all electron energies for which we had the measured photon distribution available. As can be seen in Fig.9 the computed mean C2 signal agrees very well with the accelerator measurements.

Figure 9: Comparison of the simulated (line) and measured (crosses) mean value of the photon distribution represented by the signal given in mV that is proportional to the number of photons as function of electron energy.

For protons, a minor asymmetry between simulation and calibration becomes evident. At this moment, it is not clear whether this is caused by an inaccuracy of the involved calculations or imperfect conditions at the test facility at CERN. Nevertheless, both distributions are in good agreement towards the high tails, and thus no systematic misallocation of protons in the E300 channel by exceeding the C21 threshold based on the mathematical modeling is expected.

Overall, the calibration measurements demonstrate that the simulation provides an accurate description of the C2 detector response to electrons over a wide energy range, while minor discrepancies remain for the proton measurements. The implication for the separation of protons from electrons is negligible and the uncertainty for the energy determination for protons can be minimized using the two SSDs via the $\frac{dE}{dx}$ – C-method (Heber 1997).

3.2.3 C1 Cherenkov Detector

We performed a similar analysis for the **C1** Cherenkov detector: In contrast to the **C2** signal, the **C1** signal is only transmitted for the coincidence channels E4 and E12. Although a large set of calibration runs for electrons was performed, the **C1** distribution has been evaluated only for electrons with energies of 7.5 MeV in channel E4. As can be seen in the left panel of Fig. 10 the **PHA** distributions of **C1** is well reproduced by the simulations.

For the proton measurements at 4.15 GeV, the extraction of the **C1**-distribution is not straightforward and can only be achieved if the instrument is switched into a Failure Mode (**FM**). Table 5 summarizes the implemented failure modes and their effects on the coincidence logic.

Table 5: Influence of the failure modes on the coincidence logic

Failure Mode	Detector	Simulated Signal
FM1	D1	D10 for all coincidence channels
FM2	D2	D20 for all coincidence channels
FM3	C1 / S1	C10 for P190, P4000, A190, A4000, E4, E12, E300 $\overline{C10}$ for P1, P4, P32, P116, A1, A4, A32, A116
FM4	C2	C20 for P116, P190, P4000, A116, A190, A4000, E4, E12, E300 $\overline{C20}$ for P1, P4, P32, A1, A4, A32
FM5	S2	$\overline{S20}$ for all coincidence channels
FM6	A	$\overline{A0}$ for all coincidence channels

Figure 10: **PHA** distribution of 7.5 MeV electrons and 4.15 GeV protons in C1 from the calibration (black curves) at Orme and Cern, respectively. Shown as shaded distribution are the results of the simulation. The upper panels show the residual between the measurements and simulations, indicating a good agreement between calibration and simulation.

In order to obtain the **C1**-distribution for protons **KET** was run in failure modes 3 and 5. All protons with energies of 4.15 GeV are expected to be measured in P4000, for which the **C1**-distribution is not

available. Setting **FM 5** the protons are now counted in E12. In order to obtain the number of protons that would trigger P190 instead of P4000, **FM 3** was set. Now, the threshold C10 is ignored, and all proton signals are counted in E12. Therefore, the **C1**-distribution in the right panel of Fig. 10 shows a significant number of entries that are below the nominal threshold of **C1**. Comparing the fraction of particles registered below the C10 threshold, we find a remarkable agreement of 13.8% in the simulation compared to 14.1% in the calibration. This indicates that the detector response is correctly reproduced despite differences in the low-amplitude region.

Overall, the results confirm that the simulation provides a reliable and accurate description of the C1 detector response for both electrons and protons.

3.2.4 Scintillation Detectors S2/A

So far, the **S2** detector has not been explicitly considered in the simulation, as its contribution to the coincidence logic depends solely on whether the S20 discriminator threshold is exceeded. Given the large number of Photons emitted in the NE104 scintillator material compared to the Cherenkov detectors allows to measure traversing particles with an efficiency close to 1. Setting a threshold at an energy loss of 100 keV yielded valid coincidence conditions.

The same argument and threshold is valid for the anti coincidence **A**.

3.2.5 Angular response and efficiency

In order to characterize the efficiency of the anti coincidence detector **A**, which, together with the **SSD D2**, defines the opening angle of the **KET**, the angular response was determined. Utilizing protons that penetrate the instrument, here protons at 4.15 GeV, the relative efficiency was computed from the calibration measurements and the simulation. Fig. 11 displays the values obtained from the simulation (\times) and the

Figure 11: Angular dependency of proton detection. Crossed curves represent simulation results, calibration measurements from [Sierks \(1988\)](#) are shown as dots.

calibration (\cdot). Note that particles are counted in P190 due to the inefficiency of the **C1** Cherenkov detector. The comparison shows that the simulation agrees very well with the measurements. Even the entries counted in E300 are represented. These entries are caused by hits in the quartz window of the **PM** that reads out the **C2** Cherenkov detector.

Overall, the simulation results of the S2 and A scintillator agree well with the calibration data. Thus a reliable and accurate description of the scintillator detector response is provided.

3.2.6 Energy dependent response for electron beams

Measurements of MeV electrons with instruments such as the [KET](#) aboard Ulysses require particularly thorough calibration because the detector response depends sensitively on particle energy, incidence angle, and interaction processes within the instrument. At relativistic energies, electrons produce complex signals through a combination of ionization losses, Cherenkov radiation, and shower development, all of which are strongly influenced by detector geometry, material composition, and electronic thresholds. Small uncertainties in these parameters can lead to significant biases in the derived energy spectra and intensities. Furthermore, the broad angular acceptance and multi-detector coincidence logic used for particle identification introduce additional response variations that must be accurately characterized. The last step is to determine the energy-dependent response factor of electrons.

Depending on the electron energy, we expected to count them in the three electron channels E4, E12, E300, and P4000 because the electromagnetic shower in C2 is relatively small, and the number of photons is not sufficient to trigger the threshold C21 that separates P4000 from E300.

As detailed in [Sierks \(1988\)](#), the relative response can be defined for each channel E4, E12, E300, and P4000 as the number of counts in each coincidence divided by the weighted counts in D2 (see [Fig. 3](#)). The result of this analysis is displayed in [Fig. 12](#) with the calibration and simulation results shown as crosses and dots, respectively. Taking into account the uncertainties, we find good agreement between the simulation and the measurements.

Figure 12: Detection efficiency of electrons as function of energy. Crosses mark simulation results, errorbars mark measurements at the accelerator facilities at ORME up to 140 MeV and Bonn further on. Dotted lines represent spline fits to the calibration measurements.

Ground-based calibration measurements were used to validate the GEANT4-based simulation of the **KET**. For the **SSDs** and Cherenkov detectors, the simulated pulse-height and energy-loss distributions show good agreement with calibration data over a wide range of electron energies. Minor discrepancies observed in proton measurements, particularly in the C2 detector, are limited to low-amplitude regions and do not significantly affect particle identification. The overall angular response and coincidence behavior are well reproduced by the simulation. These results demonstrate that the modeled instrument response provides a reliable basis for deriving response functions and interpreting KET flight data.

4 Computation of Omnidirectional Particle Response Functions

The close agreement between ground-based calibration measurements and the [GEANT4](#)-based simulation of the [KET](#) provides a solid foundation for the computation of instrument response functions. Since the simulated detector response reproduces the measured pulse-height distributions, angular acceptance, and coincidence behavior with sufficient accuracy, the model can be used to reliably relate measured count rates to physical particle fluxes.

For the derivation of omnidirectional response functions, an isotropic particle distribution is assumed. This approximation is well justified for electrons with energies ranging from a few MeV to several GeV, as well as for protons in the corresponding energy channels, particularly for time-integrated observations or periods when strong pitch-angle anisotropies are not dominant. Under this assumption, the detector response depends only on particle energy and instrument geometry, allowing an integration over the full solid angle of accepted trajectories (see also eq. 1).

The omnidirectional response functions are obtained by folding the simulated detection efficiencies for electrons and protons with the geometrical acceptance of the instrument and the coincidence logic defining each measurement channel. This procedure yields effective energy-dependent response functions that can be directly applied to convert measured count rates into omnidirectional particle fluxes via e.g. the Bow-Tie method (see for example [Heber et al. 2024](#); [Köberle et al. 2025c](#), and references therein). The resulting response functions constitute a key input for quantitative studies of [SEPs](#) and [GCRs](#) observed by [KET](#). The results of such computations used in the [SPEARHEAD](#) project are shown in [Fig. 13](#) and [14](#).

Left side of [Fig. 13](#) and [14](#) show the expected energy response for protons in the proton channels and electrons in the electron channels, respectively. High energy electron responses have been omitted because we want to focus here on the determination of the ultra relativistic [SEP](#) events ([Köberle et al. 2025c](#)), which have been observed to have an upper energy limit of about 100 MeV (see for example [Moses et al. 1989](#); [Dröge et al. 1989](#), and references in it) and the modulation of [GCRs](#) by Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections ([ICMEs](#)).

Right side of [Fig. 13](#) and [14](#) show the computed energy responses of protons in the electron channels and electrons in the proton channels, respectively. Protons contribute to all electron channels for energies above 2 GeV. Although the energy response seems small, the effect is clearly visible in the variation of the background at quiet times ([Heber et al. 2005](#)). This has been taken into account in [Köberle et al. \(2025c\)](#). The energy response of the electrons in the proton channel is only large for the P4000. However, since electrons are minor compared to protons this can be neglected.

Figure 13: Response functions for protons in proton channels (left) and response of protons to other species channel (right).

Figure 14: Response functions for electrons in electron channels (left) and response of electrons to other species channel (right).

Figure 15: Visualization of the Bow Tie analysis for the electron sub-channel with **C2 PHA** values from 90 to 100: **a)** Response function derived from the **GEANT4** simulation. **b)** Test spectra: Power law spectra with spectral indices from 1.4 to 5. **c)** Simulation response folded with the power law spectra. **d)** Pairs of energies and responses describing the **PHA** bin are shown for each spectral index. The area in which the lines intersect has been enlarged for better visibility. The effective energy and optimal response are marked by the black lines.

In Köberle et al. (2025c) we used **PHA** selected sub-channels of the E12. Then the Bow Tie analysis (Gieseler et al. 2024) is applied to these sub-channels to allow for a transformation of count rates into differential flux. Typically, the goal of the method is to minimize the geometric factor error (Boudouridis et al. 2020). Since our goal is to optimize the energy spectrum for individual events rather than obtain a single geometric factor representing the instrument for the whole mission, we chose a slightly different approach. In order to find a good approximation of the energies, a mean energy is determined, and the geometric factor is optimized for this energy. Figure 15 illustrates the method for the **C2 PHA** bin from 90 to 100 used in Köberle et al. (2025c).

The **GEANT4** simulation resulted in a broad response for the sub-channel, as shown in Fig. 15 a. It is folded with a set of power-law test spectra $\phi_\gamma(E) = a \cdot E^{-\gamma}$ covering a range of possible spectral indices γ (Fig. 15 b, resulting in c). The test spectra are normalized according to $\int_{E_1}^{E_2} \phi_\gamma(E) dE = 1$, where the energy range of $E_1 = 1$ MeV to $E_2 = 3$ GeV is specified by the simulation parameters.

We assume that the energy spectra of solar electrons follow a power law distribution; therefore,

power-law spectra are appropriate test spectra. This results from previous works by Moses et al. (1989) and Dröge et al. (1989) who obtained electron spectra based on ISEE-3 (ICE) measurements of electrons with energies from 0.1 to 100 MeV. They identified two groups of events: one where spectra could be described by a single power law in rigidity and another with spectra hardening at high rigidities. Heristchi & Amari (1992) converted the rigidity spectra from Moses et al. (1989) into energy spectra where both groups could be approximated by a single power-law. Studies of electrons above 10 MeV measured by the OGO 5 spacecraft confirm that solar electron spectra follow a power-law spectrum (Datlowe 1971).

After multiplying the response $r(E)$ with a test spectrum, the number of counts C_γ in the **C2 PHA** bin can be calculated for a single spectral index γ by integration:

$$C_\gamma = \int_{E_1}^{E_2} r(E) \cdot \phi_\gamma(E) dE, \quad (4)$$

or in the case of the discrete response for n energy bins,

$$C_\gamma = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i \cdot \phi_\gamma(E_i) \cdot \Delta E_i. \quad (5)$$

E_i is the mean, ΔE_i is the width, and r_i is the response of the i -th energy bin. Possible pairs of energy E and response R_γ result in the count rate C_γ :

$$C_\gamma = R_\gamma(E) \cdot \phi_\gamma(E). \quad (6)$$

The possible solutions are visualized for all test spectra in Fig. 15 d. The curves show the shape of a bow tie intersecting within a small region, the 'knot' of the bow tie. This knot marks the best pair of effective energy E_{eff} and optimal response R_{opt} to describe the bin. To approximate the effective energy, the mean of all intersections of the curves is interpreted as effective energy E_{eff} . The optimal response R_{opt} is calculated as the mean of the responses $R_\gamma(E_{\text{eff}})$ at this energy, and the error is determined by the largest difference between R_{opt} and an individual $R_\gamma(E_{\text{eff}})$.

The choice of spectral indices in the test spectra influences the results for effective energy, optimal response, and the error of the optimal response. Effective energy and optimal response are systematically shifted by increasing or decreasing the spectral indices. The statistical error of the optimal response depends on the size of the spectral range. In order to improve the results, the choice of test spectra is optimized for each event.

Assuming isotropic particle distributions, the response functions are derived for electrons and protons by considering the simulated detection efficiencies with the instrument geometry and coincidence logic. The resulting energy-dependent responses enable a reliable conversion of measured count rates into physical particle fluxes. The analysis shows that proton contamination in electron channels becomes relevant at energies above approximately 2 GeV, whereas electron contamination in proton channels is generally negligible except for the highest-energy proton channel. The response functions are particularly suited for studies of solar energetic electrons up to about 100 MeV and for investigations of galactic cosmic-ray modulation. Overall, the derived response functions provide a robust basis for quantitative analyses of high-energy particles observed by KET.

5 Conclusions

The reliability of energetic particle measurements in space depends on several factors. These include the sensitivity and calibration of the detectors used, the shielding of the instruments against background radiation, and the stability of the spacecraft's environment. To enable the scientific data analysis of Ulysses/*KET* data within *SPEARHEAD*, a determination and validation of the response function is needed. Essential for the process is a detailed model of the particle instrument.

This deliverable presents the validation of a detailed *GEANT4*-based model of the Ulysses/*KET* instrument, demonstrating good agreement with ground-based calibration and in-flight measurements for both electrons and protons. The resulting omnidirectional response functions provide a robust and reliable basis for converting *KET* count rates into physical particle fluxes, enabling quantitative studies of *SEPs*, *GCRs*, and *FDs* within the *SPEARHEAD* project.

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